

Amylose content was highest in IET4094 and lowest in IET2254. The elongation ratio of milled rice ranged between 1.74 (IR36) and 1.22 (CR237-1).

Highest volume expansion during cooking was in the CN747-8-1 and highest water uptake was in IET1444. IR42 expanded least and had low water uptake. □

Grain characteristics of some aromatic rice varieties of Assam

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Scented rice is grown by farmers in Assam for the preparation of special holiday foods. We studied awning, pigmentation, length/breadth (L/B) ratio, and 1,000-grain weight of 43 traditional scented varieties in 1988. Thirteen possessed awns and 23 were pigmented. Grain length was 5.66-9.94 mm, breadth 1.80-2.96 mm, L/B ratio 2.44-4.33, and 1,000-grain weight 8.44-25.48 g. □

Pest resistance – diseases

Blast (BI) resistance in tidal swamp rices of Indonesia

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We evaluated field resistance to B1 caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* in 158 rices during the 1988 wet season.

Each line was transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plots were fertilized with urea and triple superphosphate at 120-26 kg NP/ha. Disease scoring was one 30 d after transplanting.

None of the varieties tested were resistant; 33 were moderately resistant (MR) (see table). □

Pest resistance–insects

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge (GM)

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We field-tested 137 rice varieties and breeding lines for resistance to GM during 1987-88 wet seasons. Seedlings were transplanted 1 mo after seeding in two 4-m rows/variety at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Susceptible check TN1 was planted every 20 rows. Local recommended agronomic practices were followed.

GM incidence and damage were recorded 30 and 50 d after transplanting. Susceptible check TN1 had an average 75% infested hills and 29% silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting.

Eleven entries were found to be highly resistant to GM, three showed moderate resistance (see table).

Rice GM resistance in Manipur, India, 1987-88 wet seasons.

Cultivar	Cross	Resistance rating ^a
R320-300	Asha/Kranti	0
R321-108	Samridhi/IR36	0
RP2436-79-22-2	IR50/WGL 22508	0
WGL 18011-15	CR44/WGL 12708	0
WGL 20471-97	BC5/WGL 12708	0
WGL 26358	IR20/WGL 12708	0
BPT3624	BPT3361/WGL 26888	0
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	0
Aganni	Donor	0
T1477	Donor	0
Banglei	Donor	0
WGL 3011-120	WGL 22509/IR50	3
WGL 47998	Obs 677/IR2070	3
R320-101	Asha/Kranti	3
TN1	Susceptible check	9

^aScale 0-9 based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Reaction of tidal swamp rices to Bl. Unit Tatas, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1988 wet season.

Line	Disease score	Reaction
BRB4-29-3	3	MR
BR51-120-2	3	MR
BW100	3	MR
BW295-4	3	MR
BW295-5	3	MR
B3240 ENG 4	3	MR
Cisadane	3	MR
CR1002	3	MR
IR13149-3-2-2	3	MR
IR13149-43-2	3	MR
IR13423-17-1-2-1	3	MR
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	3	MR
IR2307-247-2-2-3	3	MR
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	3	MR
IR28223-399-5-6	3	MR
IR31662-47-2-1	3	MR
IR4-11	3	MR
IR4417-179-1-5-2	3	MR
IR4422-480-2-2-3	3	MR
IR4432-52-6-4	3	MR
IR5785-188-2-1	3	MR
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	3	MR
P1277-7-14M-5-1B	3	MR
P1342-6-10M-3-1B	3	MR
ROHY B15-WAR-3-3	3	MR
ROK5	3	MR
IR28288-12-3-1-1-2	3	MR
B4460H-MR-6	3	MR
IR19661	3	MR
Kapuas	3	MR
Cisanggarung	3	MR
BRB50-13-2-1	3	MR
DWCB-B-27-2	3	MR

Effect of temperature and storage on yellow stem borer (YSB) egg hatchability and larval survival

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Routine YSB cultures on caged plants sometimes cannot supply enough newly emerged larvae for yield-loss studies. Egg masses produced by females collected in light traps are needed. To synchronize larval emergence with experimental needs, embryonic development must be suspended. We experimented to determine the temperature regime during incubation that would not affect egg hatchability and larval survival.

Newly emerged YSB moths reared in the field on caged IR46 rice plants were collected daily and caged for oviposition on 30-d-old IR36 plants. Egg masses of uniform size were collected daily and placed singly in test tubes with a moist cotton pad at the bottom. One egg mass represented one replication. The test tubes with egg

masses were plugged and placed inside incubators at 8, 12, 15, 17, and 20 °C temperatures for 0, 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, and 21 d.

Four test tubes with egg masses per treatment were exposed at room temperature for embryonic development. The dates on which eggs hatched were recorded. Emerged larvae were counted after 4 d and egg masses were dissected to determine the number of unhatched eggs.

Ten larvae from each egg mass were caged on potted IR36 plants at the booting stage. At 24 d after infestation, the plants were dissected and larvae surviving counted.

During the cool months (Dec-Feb), YSB eggs hatched normally 8 d after oviposition. Handling delayed hatching by 1 d, regardless of incubation temperature (Fig. 1a).

Hatching could be delayed 25 d when eggs were incubated at 15 °C, and 23 d at 17 °C (Fig. 1b). Eggs stored at

Incubation period, egg hatchability, and larval survival of YSB as affected by storage period at different temperature regimes.

8 °C for 3, 6, 10, 15, and 21 d, and at 12 °C for 15 and 21 d did not hatch.

Larval survival decreased drastically with a progressive increase in storage period at low temperatures; it was least

affected when eggs were incubated at 20 °C (Fig. 1c).

For optimum hatchability and larval survival, storage of YSB egg masses should not exceed 10 d at 15 °C. □

Phenolic compounds, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in rice leaves of varieties resistant to rice thrips

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Rice varieties differ in susceptibility to the rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis*. We examined concentrations of phenolic compounds, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in the leaves of seven susceptible and six resistant varieties.

Leaves of 30-d-old healthy and infested rice plants were analyzed, with two replications per analysis. Catechol was the standard for colorimetric assay. Total phenols were separated and

estimated by silica-gel thin-layer chromatography (TLC). Salicylic acid was separated using chloroform:acetic acid (9:1 vol/vol) solvent system. Chlorogenic and gallic acids were separated using methanol:acetic acid:water (9:1:1 vol/vol) solvent system. Co-chromatography with authentic samples indicated that most of the phenols belonged to benzoic and cinnamic acid derivatives.

Resistant varieties possessed significantly higher content of total phenols (Table 1). Salicylic acid was higher in susceptible varieties, but concentrations of chlorogenic and gallic acids were higher in resistant varieties (Table 2). Reducing sugars were significantly higher in susceptible varieties. Free amino acid content was generally higher in susceptible varieties. □

Table 1. Phenols, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in healthy (H) and thrips-infested (I) plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties.

Variety	mg/g fresh weight of leaves					
	Phenols		Reducing sugars		Free amino acids	
	H	I	H	I	H	I
<i>Resistant</i>						
Ptb21	5.45	5.50	4.20	4.60	3.65	4.55
Mozhikaruppu	5.05	4.95	3.55	4.50	2.75	4.45
Kandagasalai	6.35	5.70	3.85	4.53	3.35	4.40
CO 3	5.05	5.45	2.98	3.55	2.95	3.70
TNR1	5.40	5.25	3.13	3.28	2.70	3.30
IR62	4.80	4.55	2.25	2.98	2.95	3.20
Mean	5.35	5.23	3.33	3.90	3.06	3.93
<i>Susceptible</i>						
Bhavani	3.30	3.05	6.03	5.40	3.10	3.95
ADT38	3.80	3.65	7.43	7.88	3.85	4.40
IR26	3.00	2.80	5.13	5.78	2.85	3.75
IR34	3.10	3.05	4.90	5.15	3.90	4.30
IR8	3.05	2.75	5.03	5.28	3.65	4.50
Vani	3.45	3.40	7.40	7.68	3.30	4.10
CO 43	3.45	3.15	6.08	6.35	3.25	4.10
Mean	3.31	3.12	6.00	6.36	3.41	4.16
<i>LSD values</i>						
Healthy vs infested	0.17**		0.36**		0.54**	
Resistant vs susceptible	0.17***		0.36***		0.54*	
Between varieties	0.12**		0.26**		0.39*	